

Improving the Thermochemical Energy Storage Performance of the Mn₂O₃/Mn₃O₄ Redox Couple by Fe Incorporation

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Abstract: Redox cycles of manganese oxides (Mn₂O₃/Mn₃O₄) are a promising alternative for thermochemical heat storage (TCS) systems coupled to concentrated solar power plants (CSP) since they are abundant and inexpensive materials. Although their cyclability for such a purpose has been proved, sintering processes, related to the high temperature conditions at which charge-discharge cycles are carried out, generally cause a cycle-to-cycle decrease on the oxidation rate of Mn₃O₄. In order to guarantee a proper operation, both reactions should present stable reaction rates. In this study, it has been demonstrated that incorporating Fe to the manganese oxides, which is also an abundant material, improves the redox performance of this system by increasing the heat storage density, narrowing the redox thermal hysteresis, and, above all, stabilizing and enhancing the oxidation rate over long operation, counteracting the negative effects caused by sintering, despite not avoiding its presence.

Introduction

Concentrating solar power (CSP) is meant to play a major role in achieving the targeted objectives of renewable energy generation in the next decades. This is partly due to the possibility of implementing thermal energy storage (TES) systems allowing increasing the annual capacity factor and enhancing the energy generation dispatchability.^[1,2]

The excess of heat collected by the solar field can be stored by such systems via three different mechanisms: sensible, latent and thermochemical heat storage.^[3] To date, only sensible heat storage using molten salts has been successfully implemented in commercial plants. However, new advances in central receiver plants working with volumetric air receivers will allow producing air at temperatures above 1000 °C, which is higher than the stability range of commercial salts. Relying on this fact, thermochemical heat storage (TCS) based on redox reactions of metal oxides, has emerged as a potentially more efficient and feasible option for storing excess of heat at high temperatures.^[4-7]

This type of TCS consists of two main steps. First, part of the hot air generated in the volumetric receiver is used to supply the energy required to perform the thermal reduction of the metal oxide, with its consequent release of gaseous oxygen (Equation

1). By this high-temperature endothermic process, energy collected from the sun is partly stored by means of a chemical reaction in the so-called *charge step*. During off-sun periods, *discharge* proceeds by performing the reversible reaction (Equation 2). In this case, air is used to oxidize the reduced form of the metal oxide, releasing the stored heat due to the exothermic nature of this process.

Several redox couples were analyzed by Wong *et al.*^[8] as possible candidates for this application. Among them, BaO₂/BaO, Co₃O₄/CoO and Mn₂O₃/Mn₃O₄ pairs are thermodynamically favored to operate in the 600-1000 °C temperature range. The latter presents the benefit of being more inexpensive and abundant than the rest, storing and releasing energy through the redox reactions shown in Equation 3, which have been proved to be reversible during long term charging-discharging cycling in lab scale tests.^[9]

However, sintering processes caused by the high-temperature thermal treatment led to an exponential decrease of the oxidation rate during the first cycles assayed.^[9] The durability of the chemical activity of these materials is the key factor for a successful operation of TCS. Namely, stability of the oxidation rates over long term cycling will be required for a proper control of the discharging process and guarantee the commercial viability of such technology.

In our previous work^[9] we concluded the heat transferred limited nature of the reduction reaction, whereas oxidation appeared to be controlled by diffusional phenomena, reason why we attributed the slowdown on the re-oxidation rate to sintering. In this respect, chemical or microstructural modifications of raw manganese sesquioxide are considered as the two main options in order to improve the redox properties of the Mn₂O₃/Mn₃O₄ pair. Doping with other metals has been generally studied as a first approach, since incorporation of cations of different oxidation states and radii could create charge unbalances, disorders or vacancies that could result adequate for better oxygen diffusion through the crystal lattice. However, it has not always been proved to be efficient. In the case of Co₃O₄, Agrafiotis *et al.*^[6] studied the addition of bivalent cations (Ni, Cu, Mg, Zn) to this material without any improvement on the redox behavior. On the other hand, Block *et al.*^[4] performed a complete study of the Co-Fe-O system for TCS purposes, finding that addition of Fe in small amounts (<10%) resulted beneficial to the redox behavior compared with pure Co₃O₄ over long cycling assays (> 30 cycles) in spite of slightly reducing the reaction enthalpies. For the case of Mn₂O₃, we demonstrated that addition of Co hindered the redox reversibility of this pair.^[7] Previously, Wong *et al.*^[8] studied the effect of other dopants (Fe, Cu, Li, Zr, Zn, Ni, Cr, Ti) on Mn₂O₃, preparing the mixed oxides by mechanical mixing. As they reported low re-oxidation conversions for the undoped oxide (<10%), addition of several of those metal cations enhanced the oxidation yield. Nevertheless, full re-

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oxidation was only achieved with addition of 10 % Fe₂O₃ and just for one cycle. Taking into account the above mentioned findings, in this work the influence of Fe incorporation on the redox performance of the Mn₂O₃/Mn₃O₄ pair has been studied, paying special attention to the possible improvements produced on the oxidation reaction, process highly affected by sintering phenomena.

Results and Discussion

Mn-Fe-O system

The Mn-Fe-O system has been studied in air atmosphere by several authors^[10–14] and at lower oxygen partial pressure by Azimi *et al.*^[15] and Rydén *et al.*^[16], which evaluated Mn-Fe oxides as oxygen carriers for chemical looping combustion. At temperatures around 700 °C three different regions are well identified in reported phase diagrams. Between 0 and ca. 50 mol % of Fe (% Fe = (Fe/Mn+Fe)·100) only cubic (Mn,Fe)₂O₃ (bixbyite) is observed. From that point up to ca. 90 % Fe, two crystal phases co-exist: bixbyite and hexagonal hematite, (Fe,Mn)₂O₃. Finally, up to 100 % Fe, only hematite phase is observed. Therefore, iron has large solubility into bixbyite.^[14] For higher concentrations of Mn (below 40 % Fe) at high temperatures the tetragonal spinel hausmannite, α-(Mn,Fe)₃O₄, occupies a small region of the Mn-Fe-O phase diagram, being the cubic spinel β-(Mn,Fe)₃O₄ the most stable phase in this interval. Two regions with co-existence of crystal phase can also be appreciated at intermediate temperatures. The first one with the presence of tetragonal and cubic spinels, the second, with bixbyite and cubic spinel

Based on the above mentioned results, this work has been focused in the study of manganese oxides doped with iron amounts ranging from 0 to 40 molar %, since, ideally, it is preferable not having mixtures of crystal phases, as phase segregations might cause kinetic hurdles. Therefore, the expected redox reactions in the studied system are as follows:

Table 1. Composition, crystal phase, crystallite size (*d*), cubic lattice parameter (*a*) and specific surface area (*S*_{BET}) of the as-synthesized materials. (*S*_{BET4}) is the specific surface area after four cycles.

Sample name	% mol Fe*	Crystal Phase	<i>d</i> (nm)	<i>a</i> (Å)	<i>S</i> _{BET} (m ² g ⁻¹)	<i>S</i> _{BET} (m ² g ⁻¹)
0F	0	Mn ₂ O ₃	49.4	9.411	10.4	-†
1F	0.9	Mn ₂ O ₃	43.2	9.410	10.3	1.26
5F	4.7	Mn ₂ O ₃	42.8	9.411	13.0	1.49
10F	9.2	Mn ₂ O ₃	50.0	9.409	12.2	1.07
20F	20.8	Mn ₂ O ₃	42.5	9.410	17.5	1.00
40F	41.4	Mn ₂ O ₃	49.5	9.397	18.1	1.61

*% Fe = (Fe/Mn+Fe)·100; † Too low to be determined

Physicochemical properties of as-synthesized Fe- Mn oxides

Six samples were prepared via Pechini method varying the Fe amount from 0 to 40 mol %. Table 1 summarizes the composition, crystalline properties and BET surface area of all materials. XRD analyses (Figure 1) evidenced that all of them presented cubic Mn₂O₃ crystal structure (bixbyite, ICDD 00-041-144, space group *Ia* $\bar{3}$) after calcination at 700 °C. These results agree with reported phase diagrams.^[10–14]

Figure 1. XRD patterns of the as-prepared samples. The dashed lines indicate the zone shown in the right panel, which depicts the most intense reflection used for crystallite size calculations.

Crystallite size determination (Table 1) showed that the six samples presented similar values, ranging from 42.5 to 50 nm. Thus, addition of Fe did not affect the crystallinity of the materials. Since both cations present the same ionic radius in 6-fold coordination (0.645 Å)^[17], it is expected that Fe³⁺ will partially replace the Mn³⁺ cations within the bixbyite phase, then leading to a solid solution. This was confirmed by the lattice parameter calculations as almost no variations were observed. However, 40F sample exhibited an unexpected decrease of the lattice parameter. This fact is attributed to a possible presence of tetravalent Mn cations, which present a smaller radius than Mn³⁺ (*r*_{Mn⁴⁺} = 0.53 Å). This hypothesis was confirmed observing the first heating ramp at which 40F sample was subjected, which is depicted in Figure S1 (supporting information). There it can be observed that the derivative of the weight signal presented a shoulder before the maximum. This indicates the reduction of Mn⁴⁺ into Mn³⁺, prior to the reduction of trivalent cations into divalent ones. During the next oxidation step, Mn⁴⁺ was not formed again.

Raman spectrometry (Fig. 2) was used to get further structural information about the Fe-doped Mn oxides. Raman spectra of Mn₂O₃ materials have been investigated by several authors. Nevertheless, some discrepancies in the Raman modes of these species were found in literature. Some authors^[18–20] reported a well-defined high intense Raman peak around 650 cm⁻¹, whereas other results proved black bixbyite spectra to be very weak^[20–23], presenting a characteristic mode ca. 680 cm⁻¹.^[20,21,23] However, Buciuman *et al.*^[20], which studied Raman spectra of Mn oxides, stated that, under green or more energetic light, Mn₂O₃ peak

around 650 cm^{-1} is due to the formation of Mn_3O_4 during the acquisition period. This agrees well with reported Mn_3O_4 Raman spectra^[20–22,24], which established that tetragonal hausmannite exhibits an intense Raman mode at 650 cm^{-1} , assigned to the A_{1g} mode^[21,24] corresponding to the Mn–O breathing vibration of divalent manganese ions in tetrahedral coordination^[21], and weaker modes at 310 and 370 cm^{-1} . Previously to the work of Buciuman *et al.*, Bernard *et al.*^[25] had pointed out that commercial Mn_2O_3 gave an identical spectrum to Mn_3O_4 due to overheating. As observed in Fig. 2, the hypothesis of both authors. could account for the results obtained in this work, since the Raman spectra of all the synthesized samples presented the most intense peak at 650 cm^{-1} and less intense modes around 310 and 360 cm^{-1} , with the exception of 40F sample, which showed a shift on the most intense mode to lower values (ca. 630 cm^{-1}). This fact could corroborate the aforementioned presence of Mn^{4+} cations, since MnO_2 exhibits a small band around $630\text{--}640\text{ cm}^{-1}$. Likewise, it was not observed any Raman mode around 680 cm^{-1} , which as commented before is characteristic of Mn_2O_3 . Regarding the effects caused by Fe incorporation, it can be observed in Fig. 2 that the peak intensity generally decreased with an increase of the Fe amount. This clearly indicates the decrease of the number of Mn–O bonds as the presence of Fe increases on the crystal lattice, confirming the formation of a solid solution.

Figure 2. Raman spectra of Fe- Mn oxides using 532 nm laser.

Figure 3 depicts SEM micrographs of the as-synthesized Fe-doped Mn oxides. All the powders presented a similar morphology before being subjected to the redox cycles. However, the specific surface area determined by the BET method (Table 1) showed differences for each sample. The trend observed indicates that increasing the amount of Fe, produced oxides with higher surface areas. For instance, for 0F sample it was obtained a S_{BET} value of $10.4\text{ m}^2\text{ g}^{-1}$, whereas for 40F it was $18.1\text{ m}^2\text{ g}^{-1}$. Nevertheless, these values decreased by one order of magnitude after four cycles (Table 1), as consequence of the surface reduction caused by sintering

processes related to the elevated temperatures at which redox reactions of these materials take place.

Figure 3. SEM micrographs of Fe- Mn oxides prepared via Pechini method.

Influence of Fe-doping on the reactions temperatures

One of the most remarkable characteristics of redox cycles of some metal oxides (e.g. $\text{Mn}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Mn}_3\text{O}_4$ and $\text{Co}_3\text{O}_4/\text{CoO}$) is the difference in temperature for the transition of one phase to another in the forward and reverse directions, *i.e.*, the presence of a hysteresis loop.^[7] This fact is not predicted by thermodynamic calculations based on equilibrium data or by phase diagrams, normally constructed with data of the forward reaction. The hysteresis of $\text{Mn}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Mn}_3\text{O}_4$ system, which was firstly studied by Shenouda and Aziz^[26] decades ago, shows a temperature difference between reduction and oxidation onset temperatures of ca. $200\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, whereas for $\text{Co}_3\text{O}_4/\text{CoO}$ is around $30\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.^{[4],[7]} Narrowing the hysteresis loop for the manganese oxide system means that heat is stored and released in a closer range of temperatures, which will suppose an increase of the charge-discharge energy efficiency.

Figure 4 depicts the weight loss/gain vs temperature plots for five redox cycles performed to the samples here investigated. It can be observed that increasing the addition of Fe, progressively narrows the hysteresis loop of the $\text{Mn}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Mn}_3\text{O}_4$ redox system. In the case of adding 40 % of Fe, the difference between the onset temperatures of reduction and oxidation for the 3rd cycle is $105\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (Table 2), which is ca. $175\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ of decrease with respect to the undoped Mn oxide. This narrowing of the hysteresis loop is mainly caused by the raise of the oxidation temperature, which is higher than for reduction. For instance, when comparing 0F and 40F samples it can be observed an increase of $60\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for reduction temperature, whereas for oxidation is $236\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The increase observed in the reduction temperature when raising the amount of Fe was in accordance with reported phase diagrams

for the Mn-Fe-O system^[10–14]. In summary, addition of Fe shifted the redox reaction to higher temperatures, this effect being more pronounced in the case of oxidation, causing a remarkable narrowing of the thermal hysteresis.

Table 2 Reduction and oxidation onset temperatures for the third redox cycle. Last column shows the difference between both temperatures, which gives a value for the thermal hysteresis.

Sample	$T_{\text{onset red}} (^{\circ}\text{C})$	$T_{\text{onset OX}} (^{\circ}\text{C})$	$\Delta T_{\text{Hysteresis}}$
0F	948	667	281
1F	964	728	236
5F	979	828	151
10F	993	864	129
20F	995	882	113
40F	1008	903	105

Figure 4. Weight variation versus temperature plot of three redox cycles (2nd to 4th) for the six Fe- Mn oxides.

Influence of Fe-doping on the oxidation kinetics

As stated in the introduction, the durability of the redox cycles, *i.e.* the capacity to withstand numerous charge-discharge cycles, is among the key properties that materials for this purpose must present. However, the high temperature conditions at which reduction and oxidation reactions of TCS materials take place lead to a complete morphology change due to sintering processes. Sintering, which is normally a combination of densification and coarsening phenomena^[27], hinders the diffusion of oxygen through the Mn_3O_4 material, by causing either the reduction of active surface or a high degree of particle aggregation after few redox cycles. In a previous work^[9] it has been observed that initial particle size plays an important role on the way that powders sintered, namely, larger primary particles led to more open macroporous structures that facilitated oxygen transport through the powder. Nevertheless, even if the particle size is tailored, an exponential decrease on the oxidation rate is observed due to particle coarsening. As well, it was remarkable that thermal reduction of Mn_2O_3 was not affected by sintering as in the case of Mn_3O_4 oxidation. This fact is attributed to the heat

transfer limitation of the reduction process of metal oxides, hypothesis that will be discussed later.

Figure 5. Weight variation versus time plot of ten redox cycles (10th to 20th) for the six Fe- Mn oxides.

In order to check the durability of these redox materials, they were subjected to 30 charge-discharge cycles, heating up to 1050 °C and cooling down to 650 °C (Figure S2). The weight loss/gain was monitored by TGA. Figure 5 shows the obtained curves in more detail from the 10th to 20th cycle as a representation of the reversibility of the six Mn-Fe oxides. There, it can be more clearly observed the main differences between redox cycles of each sample, namely in the weight gain step, which accounts for the oxidation reaction. While Fe-doped materials, 1F-40F, showed complete conversions for each reaction, which corresponds to a weight loss/gain percentage of 3.4 % given by the stoichiometry of eq. 4, 0F sample presented incomplete conversion even for the first oxidation (98 % which corresponded to a 3.34 % of weight gain). For this sample without Fe content, the conversion gradually decreased along the cycles. For instance, on the 25th cycle 87 % of conversion was observed for the oxidation reaction. However, in our previous works^{[7],[9]} the total reversibility of $\text{Mn}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Mn}_3\text{O}_4$ redox pair was demonstrated. Only one difference regarding the cycling conditions was changed: the maximum temperature (T_{max}) used was 1000 °C instead of 1050 °C. This fact indicates that increasing T_{max} 50 °C had a remarkable negative effect on the cyclability of the undoped sample. In order to check this fact, a 30 redox cycle analysis was carried out to the 0F sample, but decreasing T_{max} to 1000 °C. Figure S3 depicts a comparison of some redox cycles for both assays. It can be appreciated that, when the cycles are performed with a T_{max} equal to 1000 °C the oxidation and reduction reactions presented weight variations of 3.4 %, which is the theoretical value for such reactions. On the other hand, with T_{max} equal to 1050 °C a lower reduction degree was observed as commented above. This lack of total reversibility is the result of a slowdown of the oxidation. Figure 6 shows the cycle-to-cycle evolution of the oxidation rate of 0F samples for both analyses, with T_{max} of 1000 °C (0F-1000) and 1050 °C (0F-1050), respectively. By using the cycling conditions

of the former case, oxidation rate presented a 2-fold enhancement. In both cases, there is a strong drop on the reaction rate, which decays after a certain number of cycles. This first drop is more drastic for the assay 0F-1050, and it is attributed to a faster sintering effect on the first heating ramp caused by the higher temperature employed. This was confirmed by SEM micrographs taken after 30 redox cycles (inset of Figure 6) where it is clear a higher sintering extent for the particles subjected to cycles with T_{\max} of 1050 °C.

Figure 6. Effect of maximum temperature on the oxidation kinetics of 0F sample. Inset: SEM pictures after 30 cycles using $T_{\max}=1000$ °C and $T_{\max}=1050$ °C respectively.

Figure 7. SEM micrographs taken after the 30 redox cycles assays.

As it can be observed in the SEM micrographs depicted in Figure 7, after the 30 cycles assay the Fe-doped materials also presented a high degree of sintering, which, as commented before, is the principal cause for the cycle-to-cycle decay on the oxidation rate. However, doping with certain amounts of Fe remarkably changed such behavior, counteracting the kinetic hurdles caused by sintering.

Figure 8. Cycle-to-cycle evolution of the oxidation rate for the 30-redox cycles assay.

This can be observed in Figure 8, where oxidation rate evolution for the 30 charge-discharge cycles is depicted for each sample. Addition of 1 % Fe, not only produced full reversibility over the 30 cycles in the conditions assayed, but also a 2-fold increase in the oxidation rate values. However, 1F sample was also highly affected by sintering during the first five cycles presenting an exponential decrease of the oxidation rate values, which were stabilized in the subsequent cycles. In Figure S4 it can be appreciated the high degree of sintering that each sample already reached after 5 redox cycles. Incrementing the amount of Fe to 5 % counteracted such decrease on the first cycling stage, showing faster rates than 1F sample and a more gradual decay on the oxidation rate during the cycling test. Increasing to 10 % of Fe raised the oxidation rates values, but this sample showed worse rate stability than 5 F. The most remarkable effect was observed when adding iron amounts over 20 %. In this way, 40F sample presented the fastest oxidation reaction observed for the 3rd redox cycle ($0.110 \text{ mmol O}_2 \text{ min}^{-1} \text{ g}_{\text{ox}}^{-1}$). Nevertheless, after reaching this maximum, the rate values linearly decreased down to $0.087 \text{ mmol O}_2 \text{ min}^{-1} \text{ g}_{\text{ox}}^{-1}$ on the last cycles. In this respect, 20F sample presented not only the best cycle-to-cycle stability among all the Fe-doped Mn oxides assayed, but also, on average, the fastest oxidation kinetics. For this sample the oxidation rate reached a plateau after the 7th cycle, showing stable values around $0.101 \text{ mmol O}_2 \text{ min}^{-1} \text{ g}_{\text{ox}}^{-1}$ on the last ten cycles, which means only reduction of ca. 6% of the maximum value. Moreover, comparing with the pure Mn_2O_3 sample (0F), it presented almost a 5-fold enhancement of the oxidation rate values (3.5-fold if redox cycles of 0F sample are carried out with $T_{\max}=1000$ °C) during the last redox cycles.

In summary, the general trend indicates that an increase on the quantity of Fe improved the Mn_3O_4 oxidation kinetics for the conditions assayed. The results suggest that Fe-doped Mn oxides are perfect candidates for working in more severe thermal conditions.

Influence of heating/cooling ramp on the redox reaction rates

As commented before, in our previous work^[9] we attributed the decay on the oxidation rate to oxygen diffusion hindrances caused by sintering. As well, it was proposed that this fact did not apply to the reduction, as reduction values were stable over a 30 charge-discharge cycles assay, since this reaction was limited by heat transfer. This heat-transfer-limited nature of the reduction reaction of metal oxides has been reported previously for the case of ceria^{[28],[29]} used for water and CO_2 splitting via redox cycles. Rudisill *et al.*^[29] proved this behavior by carrying out the reduction at low and high heating rates. They observed that high heating rates resulted in a faster O_2 evolution, *i.e.*, a more rapid reduction rate. As it can be observed in Figure 9A, the reduction of undoped Mn_2O_3 (0F sample) also followed such behavior, the fastest the heating rate used in the charge step, the fastest the reaction was. In this case, 0F and 20F samples were subjected to one redox cycle, heating up to 1000 and 1050 °C respectively and cooling down to 500 °C under an air flow of 100 ml min^{-1} . Four different assays were carried out using 5, 10, 15 and 20 °C min^{-1} heating/cooling ramps. Nevertheless, using higher cooling rates had the opposite effect for the oxidation of Mn_3O_4 , since it slowed down its rate as the cooling rate was increased. In Figure 9B it can be appreciated that such increase in the cooling rate caused an incomplete conversion when cooling rates over 10 °C min^{-1} were used. By increasing the cooling rate, O_2 had less time to fully oxidize Mn_3O_4 before reaching temperature conditions in which reduction became thermodynamically favorable (heating ramp of the following cycle). However, this behavior was not observed for 20 F sample. For this material both reduction and oxidation reactions experienced an increase in their rate values when higher heating and cooling rates, respectively, were used (Figure 9A), leading always to full conversion. It is especially remarkable that, in the case of oxidation, addition of proper amounts of Fe enhances the flexibility of the material in terms of operation conditions. Moreover, doping with Fe could somehow change the diffusion-limited nature of Mn_3O_4 oxidation, as for 20F sample reduction and oxidation followed similar trends, although for faster heating/cooling rates reduction showed higher reaction rates. However, it is not clear yet how Fe-doping is altering the oxidation reaction. One possible explanation for the oxidation rate enhancement with increasing Fe amount (Fig. 8) could lay on the oxidation temperature increase observed with Fe concentration. This fact may indicate a kinetic-limited nature since the materials presenting higher oxidation temperatures showed higher oxidation rates. Nevertheless, a more detailed kinetic analysis, in which several reaction and material configurations^[30,31] could be applied in order to discern the actual limiting phenomena and reaction mechanism, should be performed in a future work.

Reduction rates for 20F sample showed lower values than for 0F under the heating rates assayed. This can be also seen in Figure S5, where the cycle-to-cycle evolution of reduction rate values is shown. The general trend indicated that reduction was a 2-fold faster reaction than oxidation. However, for reduction it cannot be inferred the same relation as for oxidation, since in this case gradual addition of Fe did not lead to a gradual increase of the reaction rate. In particular, 1F, 5F and 20F samples, presented the most stable reduction rate values during the 30-cycles assay, whereas, 10F and 40F presented a similar decrease as for the oxidation rate evolution. Within the assayed samples, 1F presented the fastest reaction rates. Nevertheless, it should be noted that the determined reduction rate values ranged in a narrower interval than for oxidation.

Figure 9. A: Influence of heating/cooling rate on the reduction and oxidation rate. B: Oxidation extent (α) versus temperature for the first oxidation step of 0F sample, varying the cooling rate. It should be noted that oxidation takes place from higher to lower temperatures.

Influence of Fe-doping on the heat storage density

Finally, the influence that Fe incorporation has on the capacity to store and release heat was analyzed by DSC measurements. Table 3 collects the reduction and oxidation enthalpies determined for the first charge-discharge cycle (first redox cycle heat flow *versus* temperature curves are depicted in Figure S6). A value of -184 kJ kg^{-1} was obtained for the reduction enthalpy of 0F sample, value close to the theoretical one (202 kJ kg^{-1}). However, oxidation enthalpy was lower (155 kJ kg^{-1}), giving a heat released/stored ratio of 0.84. These values decreased for 1F sample, but showed a remarkable increase for 5F sample, and, especially, for 20F sample. The former presented

enthalpies of -212 and 169 kJ kg⁻¹, for reduction and oxidation respectively, while increasing the Fe amount to 20% resulted in an increase of both reaction enthalpies, namely, -219 and 203 kJ kg⁻¹ for reduction and oxidation respectively, which for the oxidation represents an increase of ca. 30% in respect to the undoped Mn oxide. In their calculations, Rydén *et al.*^[16] previously reported a similar increase on the reaction enthalpy for a Mn oxide with 20% of Fe content, (Mn_{0.8}Fe_{0.2})₂O₃, in comparison with pure Mn₂O₃. Besides presenting the highest redox enthalpies, 20F sample also showed an elevated heat stored/released ratio (0.93) for the first cycle.

Table 3 Reduction and oxidation enthalpies for the first redox cycle. Last column shows the ratio between both values.

Sample	ΔH_{red} (kJ/kg)	ΔH_{ox} (kJ/kg)	Ratio ox/red
0F	-184	155	0.84
1F	-178	111	0.62
5F	-212	169	0.80
10F	-162	157	0.97
20F	-219	203	0.93
40F	-141	127	0.90

Conclusions

It has been demonstrated that adding Fe to the Mn oxides influenced positively on the redox performance of such materials for thermochemical heat storage applications. The incorporation of Fe resulted especially beneficial in enhancing the oxidation rate and improving its stability over 30 redox cycles. It was also observed that increasing the quantity of Fe reduced the thermal hysteresis that the Mn₂O₃/Mn₃O₄ redox couple presented, which is one of the main drawbacks in comparison with other redox pairs used for the same purpose.

In particular, doping Mn₂O₃ with 20% Fe showed the fastest and most stable oxidation reactions. This material (20F), also presented the highest energy storage density, as it showed higher enthalpy values than the other samples for both redox reactions. The combination of these two improvements, namely increased cycle stability and enhanced energy storage capacity, together with the low cost and toxicity of Fe, render such material in an attractive option for its further study and implementation as a TCS system.

Experimental Section

Materials preparation

Oxides were prepared by a modification of Pechini method, following the steps described by Jana *et al.*^[32] A certain amount of citric acid (CA) was dissolved into 50 ml of distilled water (Milli-Q) and stirred at 70 °C until complete dissolution of the CA. Then the metal (Me) precursors were added to the solution with a Me:CA molar ratio of 1:5. The following metal nitrates were used for the synthesis without further purification: Mn(NO₃)₂·4 H₂O (97 %) and Fe(NO₃)₃·9 H₂O (Sigma-Aldrich, 99.9%). After stirring for 3 h at 70 °C, the temperature of the solution was

increased to 90 °C, and then ethylene glycol (EG) was added with a molar ratio of CA:EG = 3:2. The resulting solution was further stirred at that temperature to remove the excess of solvent during 2 h. Then, the obtained resin was subsequently dried in an oven at 200 °C for 3 h and then calcined at 450 °C for 4 h in air to obtain the metal oxides. After this step, a foam was formed, which was ground with an agate mortar. Finally, the fine powders were calcined under static air at 700 °C for 4 h, using a heating rate of 2 °C min⁻¹. In total six samples with compositions varying from 0 to 40 Fe mol% were synthesized. For the sake of brevity, samples were named according to their composition as presented in Table 1.

Materials characterization

Powder X-ray diffraction (XRD) analyses were carried out employing a Philips PW 3040/00 X'Pert MPD/MRD diffractometer using CuK α radiation ($\lambda = 1.54178 \text{ \AA}$) at a scanning rate of 0.2° s⁻¹. The crystallite size was determined from the most intense reflection, according to the Scherrer formula. Cubic lattice parameter was measured applying the Bragg law and the equation $d^2 = a^2 / (h^2 + k^2 + l^2)$, where h , k and l are the Miller indexes of the Bragg plane, a is the cell parameter and d the interplanar spacing. The specific surface area (S_{BET}) was determined by nitrogen adsorption-desorption analyses at 77 K applying the multi-point BET method and using a Quantachrome QuadraSorb-S equipment. Degassing was carried out at 250 °C under vacuum. The chemical composition of the synthesized materials was obtained by inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometry (ICP-OES), using a Perkin Elmer Optima 3300 DV equipment. Samples were previously digested in acid media in an Anton Paar Multi-wave 3000 microwave. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images were taken with a XL 30 ESEM Philips microscope. Samples were sputtered with Au before the analyses. Raman spectra were recorded at room temperature using JASCO NRS-5000/7000 series Raman spectrometer with the excitation of the sample at 532 nm.

Redox cycles analyses

Stability of redox cycles was monitored by thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) using a SDT Q-600 from TA Instruments. In a typical run, 10 mg of material were placed into a 90 μ l alumina crucible and subjected to 30 cycles of heating up to 1050 °C and subsequent cooling down to 650 °C. Heating and cooling rates were of 5 °C min⁻¹ and a constant air flow of 100 ml min⁻¹ was used. Heat release and uptake was measured by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) with a TGA/DSC/1100 from Mettler-Toledo. Samples were subjected to one heating-cooling cycle under the same conditions as for TGA. Alumina crucibles of 70 μ l of capacity were used without any cap. Similar amount of material as for TGA assays was loaded in each analysis. A blank carried out in the aforementioned conditions was subtracted to each analysis to correct weight signal drifts. In order to study the influence of thermal cycling on the surface area, a larger quantity of material than the obtained after the TGA redox cycles was needed. Thus 4 redox cycles were carried out in a tubular furnace under a dynamic air flow of 100 ml min⁻¹, using the same temperature profile.

Acknowledgements

This work has received financial support from the projects TCS Power of the FP7 (ENERGY.2011.2.5-1) and MULTISTOR (ENE2012-36937) of the Spanish Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness.

Keywords: energy storage • concentrated solar power • thermochemical heat storage • redox cycles • manganese oxides

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Entry for the Table of Contents

FULL PAPER

Mn₂O₃/Mn₃O₄ redox couple performance for thermochemical heat storage was highly improved by addition of 20% Fe. Oxidation kinetics was enhanced by the presence of Fe³⁺, counteracting the limitations caused by particle sintering.

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Improving the Thermochemical Energy Storage Performance of the Mn₂O₃/Mn₃O₄ Redox Couple by Fe Incorporation